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A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF COLLECTIVE FARMING OF WOMEN IN RURAL DEVELOPMENT AND INCLUSIVE GROWTH

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Abstract

There was a time when our grandparents use to depend their livelihood especially fro the agriculture. But as the day passed the importance given to the agriculture has gradually decreased, due to various reasons. Less than 50% of people are now in to this sector. We the people in India had given agriculture as a primary sector for the purpose of the development in terms of economic policy, in each budget the agriculture will get a major portion of the budget to for the development of the agriculture. If India will concentrate now for the purpose of inclusive growth from the point of view of collective farming from women and rural development then this will have a major positive impact on the agricultural sector. Collective farming is not a new concept for the rural people, this trend has been with them for a long time and now the strengthening of these kind is essential for the rural growth. The NGO like self help group, women's associations in the rural areas like yuvati mandala, may have to take a lead to the initiation of the collective farming.

Key words: Collective Farming, Rural Development, Inclusive Growth

Introduction

Rural development is not possible unless we concentrate on the minute aspect of the work style and understand their problem . One of the problem that agriculture industry is facing is that shortage of labor. For that collective farming is n effective tool to solve the problem. This has a link to the rural development and then to the inclusive growth.

Objective of the study:

The main intention of this paper is to analyze the importance of agricultural sector in India and the positive impact of collective farming of women and the rural developments.

Methodology used:

The analysis in this paper has been done on the basis of the secondary data collected from published source. As paper focuses mainly on collective farming from women and rural development and the inclusive growth the relevant data are taken from various published article from government, non government report reports from agricultural department est.

Scope of the study:

This study covers the aspect of collective farming of women in India and its importance and also various hurdle and advantage of collective farming and also need for the strategy that we need to take and also the summary of findings .

Collective farming:

A collective farming is a farming where a few farmers can do their farming together .Here they share their ideas ,skills and knowledge with one another so that they all can produce good crops .They can easily get loan from banks .They don't have to face the blackmails of money lenders .These are the main advantages of collective farming.

A farm especially in a Communist country formed from many small holdings collected into a single unit for joint operation under governmental supervision. Collective farming in women is one where in the small self help group come to existence and it will concentrate on the farming by solving various problem faced by the farmers, By doing so one can reduce labor cost and also a sustainable growth and yield.

BACKGROUND

Although agriculture contributes only 21% of India's GDP, its importance in the country's economic, social, and political fabric goes well beyond this indicator. The rural areas are still home to some 72 percent of the India's 1.1 billion people, a large number of whom are poor. Most of the rural poor depend on rain-fed agriculture and fragile forests for their livelihoods.

The sharp rise in food grain production during India's Green Revolution of the 1970s enabled the country to achieve self-sufficiency in food grains and stave off the threat of famine. Agricultural intensification in the 1970s to 1980s saw an increased demand for rural labor that raised rural wages and, together with declining food prices, reduced rural poverty.

Sustained, although much slower, agricultural growth in the 1990s reduced rural poverty to 26.3 percent by 1999/00. Since then, however, the slowdown in agricultural growth has become a major cause for concern. India's rice yields are one-third of China's and about half of those in Vietnam and Indonesia. With the exception of sugarcane, potato and tea, the same is true for most other agricultural commodities.

The Government of India places high priority on reducing poverty by raising agricultural productivity. However, bold action from policymakers will be required to shift away from the existing subsidy-based regime that is no longer sustainable, to build a solid foundation for a highly productive, internationally competitive, and diversified agricultural sector.

Advantage and Disadvantages of collective farming:

The farmer's collectives will get support from their neighbouring landholding farmers. The landed farmers help and encourage these women by providing the raw materials such as cow dung, cow urine which are required for bio input preparation. This relationship has also led to a process of learning and sharing between landless women farmers and the landholding farmers. There are challenges too, like the delays in monsoon and frequent power cuts. Also the soil of the collective land is of very low quality and almost dead. It needs more organic inputs to regenerate. Not being disheartened with these challenges, these women discuss alternative farming methods to overcome them. They will be confident that continuous application of bio inputs will help in improving the soil health which will result in better incomes in future. Considering the high cost involved in purchase of seeds for their farming activities, the women's groups are planning to develop seed producers in their group and establish a seed bank in their village. The allotment of the work is decided in the weekly meetings during the cultivation period. All the farm works are shared equally by all members using a revolving system of labour so that all the members are engaged in all type of farm activities. As the focus of collective farming is primarily on meeting family food needs, right now, they are not marketing their produce. The produce from the collective farming provides food for the family for at

least 15 days in a month. Weeds harvested in collective farms are also being used as fodder for the livestock.

Women in agriculture:

Women represent one of the crucial development force in the world. As per the World Economic Profile, they form 50% of the World's Population, contribute 60% working force, making up to 30% of the official labour force and contribute 50% in the food production (FAO). At the home front, nearly 84% of all economically active women in India are engaged in agriculture and allied activities. Agriculture employs 4/5th of all economically active women; they make 1/3rd of the agriculture labour force and 48% self-employed farmers. There are 75 Million women as against 15 million men in dairying, the number of women engaged in animal husbandry accounts for 20 million (as against 1.5 million men)

ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

Slow Down in Agricultural and Rural Non-Farm Growth: Both the poorest as well as the more prosperous 'Green Revolution' states of Punjab, Haryana and Uttar Pradesh have recently witnessed a slow-down in agricultural growth. Some of the factors hampering the revival of growth are:

- **Poor composition of public expenditures:** Public spending on agricultural subsidies is crowding out productivity-enhancing investments such as agricultural research and extension, as well as investments in rural infrastructure, and the health and education of the rural people. In 1999/2000, agricultural subsidies amounted to 3 percent of GDP and were over 7 times the public investments in the sector.
- **Over-regulation of domestic agricultural trade:** While economic and trade reforms in the 1990s helped to improve the incentive framework, over-regulation of domestic trade has increased costs, price risks and uncertainty, undermining the sector's competitiveness.
- **Government interventions in labor, land, and credit markets:** More rapid growth of the rural non-farm sector is constrained by government interventions in factor markets -- labor, land, and credit -- and in output markets, such as the small-scale reservation of enterprises.
- **Inadequate infrastructure and services in rural areas.**

New strategy for development and sustainability:

Inclusive growth must happen from the basic level especially we need to concentrate on all the 3 sector for the successful growth of our economy. We are in 2014 middle, we talk about modernization technology adoption etc but do we really doing and applying that for the successive growth... is a question of thinking. Thus now we need to think strategically how and to what extent we can develop the primary sector and to see the sustainable development. this particular development is a long-term oriented thus for the better economy and the better future of India we need to take a strong step ahead right now only thus now it is a time to take the initiation by the government to look the agricultural sector from the new angle all together.

Summary of findings:

Bringing women into Self Help Groups (SHGs) has emerged as one of the most successful achievements of the women specific projects in Agriculture Sector. These Self Help Groups were not the part of the original project design but grew directly out of the experiences gained in early stages of these project implementation and they are now viewed as key institutions, which are vital to ensure the sustainability of project interventions. To ensure a high level of women's participation in the project process, it is essential to address the women as a 'Group' this collectivization is in itself an Empowerment Strategy

and laid the foundation for formation of Self Help Groups. The majority of the Self Help Groups are of women only, and are highly participatory, providing unique opportunities to help women to grow in self confidence and take more active role both in community and decision making process which affects their own life. These Farm Women Groups are being equipped through skill up gradation, specialized training and extension activities to undertake more remunerative on farm and off farm activities. Women are being trained in different specialized areas like Crop Husbandry, Animal Husbandry, Horticulture, Bio and Organic Farming etc. Training is also being provided to them in communication, managerial, administrative, accounting and entrepreneurship skills, in order to aid them with confidence to deal with officials. Women members of these groups are also being taught to take up group activities like food processing, value addition, packaging and marketing. Special Facility Centers are being developed where these women groups can collectively work to market their produce.

Agriculture is only a sector which is being neglected by people without knowing the importance of it. Thus when we talk about the inclusive growth the real growth must happen in the agriculture sector not only in particular city or state but in all over India the stability in terms of production, quality, maintenance ect, Should happen simultaneously. Women collective farming is one in which the women from a particular region get together and they form a particular association as a women self help group and then they collectively work at the field of each member and they could earn by doing s as well. This particular will lead to a greater yield and this will help to minimize the loss for the farmer. When we compare our cultivation with that of other nation especially in South Canara people do now following Japan type of cultivation for th purpose of increasing the yield. If the same thing will happen from a small type of association by women then the problem of various nature could be solve. In almost all the villages in India, there are about 20-30% of women who remain single, either as widows or abandoned by their families and society, who individually shoulder the burden of caring children and elders in their families. These women are either landless or have very small pieces of fragmented rain fed lands. Owing to lack of resources to invest on their own land and lack of capacities to manage their farms, these women end up doing low skilled tasks in agriculture and cattle rearing, mostly as wage laborers. Thus collective farming in the women in rural area will have a positive result at the end.

Like most other developing countries, India has predominantly been an agrarian economy, with agriculture sector contributing the largest share to gross domestic product (GDP) and employment. Under the colonial regime, Indian agriculture was geared towards the production of commercial crops (tea, coffee, rubber, cotton, etc.), while the food crops suffered from neglect. After independence, India depended heavily on imports of food grains as it inherited a stagnant, low-productivity, food-crop sector. At the time of independence, the share of agriculture in total GDP was more than 55 per cent and about 70 per cent of the population was dependent on the agriculture sector for their livelihood. In the post-independence era, stagnant production, low productivity, traditional technology, and poor rural infrastructure were the major challenges for the Government. Not surprisingly, food self-sufficiency became a key national policy goal. To achieve this goal, agricultural development received the highest priority and in the First Five Year Plan, about 17.5 per cent of the plan outlay was allocated to agriculture and about 22 per cent to irrigation, multi-purpose irrigation, and power projects. However, in the Second Five Year Plan, the emphasis shifted from labour-intensive agriculture and small scale production to large-scale capital-intensive heavy industry (Dantwala, 1986). Consequently, foodgrains production during the first three Five Year Plans remained stagnant, and India faced crisis in food production. The introduction of high yielding varieties (HYV) technology (commonly known as Green Revolution) in mid-1960s yielded spectacular results and the production of foodgrains increased from about 83.4 million tonnes in the triennium ending (TE) 1964-65 to 104.4 million tonnes in TE 1971-72 (GoI, 2012). Subsequently, the country, which was threatened by hunger and high dependence on imports as late as in mid- 1960s, became one of the largest producers of many agricultural commodities such as rice, wheat, pulses, fruits and vegetables, etc., thus being self sufficient in staple foods. In aggregate, the food situation is quite favourable in the country and the problem of hunger is one of access and income distribution rather than shortages. Today, about 407 million people in India live below poverty line (GoI, 2009) and about 42 per cent of all children under 5 years suffer from malnutrition (HUNGaMASurvey Report,2011). Increase in demand for food due to increasing population, rising income levels, and other demographic changes

will require continuous in- strregric issues and policy options, developments for inclusive growth. However, growth in productivity is slowing down in many states while the scope for expanding the area under cultivation as well as irrigation is limited. The growing environmental and natural resources concerns and food safety and human health issues associated with agriculture could threaten sustainability of agricultural growth. Therefore, the real challenges for agricultural sector in future would be to feed the ever growing population and to protect long term sustainable productive capacity of natural resource like land and water. In this paper, we analyze the dynamics of structural transformation of the Indian economy and major drivers of transformation, giving an overview of the past achievements and future challenges of Indian agriculture, finally identifying the key policy issues and strategies to accelerate sustainable broad-based growth in the agriculture sector in the country. Thus we need to accelerate the economy's growth by collective growth.

Conclusion

Despite a strong growth linkage between agriculture and other economic sectors, and poverty reduction, agriculture has not received the required attention during the reforms period. The neglect of agriculture and rapid growth of non-agriculture sector has led to serious agrarian crisis and increased disparity between urban and rural incomes. There has been some revival in the recent period as agricultural GDP growth accelerated to about 3.6 per cent during 2007-08 to 2010-11 but is still below the 4.0 per cent target for the Eleventh Plan. High food inflation due to increase and volatility in world prices as well as drought in 2009 has adversely affected the inclusive growth objective. Many factors have contributed to the slowdown in agricultural growth: inadequacies of the provision of the critical public goods such as research, extension, rural infrastructure (on which agricultural growth depends), increased competition for resources from other sectors /programmes such as rural development and poverty alleviation, and subsidies; lack of long-term government commitment required for agricultural development. To get agriculture back on broader development agenda, substantial increase in investment in agriculture research hand development, rural infrastructure, post-harvest and market infrastructure including storage and processing, reforms in laws related to land markets and marketing of agricultural products, promotion of farmers' organization/groups, Self Help Groups, etc., and appropriate agricultural price and food procurement and distribution policy are needed. In addition, pricing of inputs such as electricity, irrigation water, and fertilizer needs rationalization are required. Farm subsidies should be rationalized and better targeted to benefit the poor. These subsidies are justified as they benefit not only producers but the society at large. Agricultural price policy has played an important role in Indian agriculture but is facing some challenges. The price support policy should follow the strategy of technological change which requires more emphasis on non-price factors. Issues related to distributional aspects of agricultural credit including better access to small and marginal farmers, decline in rural branches, declining share of direct credit and significant regional and inter-class inequalities need to be addressed. Moreover, there is a need to follow multi-dimensional model of organization and management, which requires integration of agri-input, agri-production, and agro-processing and marketing segments of the value chain. Restructuring of the existing research and development institutions to make them demand driven and more responsive to the needs of users like 16 farmers and industry, and participation of the private sector, particularly in post-harvest activities including storage, food processing, and marketing should be promoted.

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